

This paper appears in *Marine Geophysical Researches*, 18:1-12, 1996.

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A Map Series of the Southern East Pacific Rise and Its Flanks, 15° S to 19° S

Abstract

Four large-scale bathymetric maps of the Southern East Pacific Rise and its flanks between 15 S and 19 S display many of the unique features of this superfast spreading environment, including abundant seamounts (the Rano Rahi Field), axial discontinuities, discontinuity migration, and abyssal hill variation. Along with a summary of the regional geology, these maps will provide a valuable reference for other sea-going programs on- and off-axis in this area, include the Mantle ELeCtromagnetic and Tomography (MELT) experiment.

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